

Data Management Plan

Version 0

Description

This deliverable reflects the data management activities of the TIER2 project. TIER2 emphasises on next-level reproducibility tools, practices & policies across diverse epistemic contexts to increase trust, integrity, & efficiency in research. In this context, TIER2 will itself adhere to radical reproducibility & transparency to ensure best practices, including adherence to Horizon Europe requirements on Research Data Management & Open Science. At the meta-level, the DMP of the project will progressively incorporate elements of reproducible research to realise a prototype of a new concept towards “Reproducibility Management Plans (RMPs)”. This enhancement will be equally supported by the development of the Reproducibility Management Plan tool that is expected to be completed at the course of the project’s lifetime.

Funder

European Commission||
EC

Grant

TIER2: ENHANCING
TRUST, INTEGRITY AND
EFFICIENCY IN RESEARCH
THROUGH NEXT-LEVEL
REPRODUCIBILITY IMPACT
PATHWAYS/ No
101094817

Researchers

Organizations

Datasets

Title: [OpenAIRE Graph Dump](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

The OpenAIRE Graph is exported as several dumps, so you can download the parts you are interested into.

publication_[part].tar: metadata records about research literature (includes types of publications listed [here](#))

dataset_[part].tar: metadata records about research data (includes the subtypes listed [here](#))

software.tar: metadata records about research software (includes the subtypes listed [here](#))

otherresearchproduct_[part].tar: metadata records about research products that cannot be classified as research literature, data or software (includes types of products listed [here](#))

organization.tar: metadata records about organizations involved in the research life-cycle, such as universities, research organizations, funders.

datasource.tar: metadata records about data sources whose content is available in the OpenAIRE Graph. They include institutional and thematic repositories, journals, aggregators, funders' databases.

project.tar: metadata records about project grants.

relation_[part].tar: metadata records about relations between entities in the graph.

communities_infrastructures.tar: metadata records about research communities and research infrastructures

Each file is a tar archive containing gz files, each with one json per line. Each json is compliant to the schema available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7492151>. The documentation for the model is available at <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/data-model/>

Learn more about the OpenAIRE Graph at <https://graph.openaire.eu>.

Discover the graph's content on [OpenAIRE EXPLORE](#) and our [API for developers](#).

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Re-using contextualised data from the OpenAIRE Graph to facilitate T2.3 in creating graphs based on indicators for reproducibility.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

OpenAIRE aggregates millions of metadata about entities of the research life-cycle, combines them and enriches them to generate the OpenAIRE Research Graph. Data empowering the OpenAIRE Graph are compiled from +130K national, institutional, academic and research sources (<https://explore.openaire.eu/search/find/dataproviders>) which are deduplicated, enhanced and contextualised. The graph is then made publicly available and used by many OpenAIRE products targeting different stakeholders, such as researchers, funders, content providers, organisations, research infrastructures and communities.

1.1.5 What is its format?

- MPEG-1 Elementary Stream
- MPEG-2 Elementary Stream
- StarOffice Calc
- StarOffice Calc
- StarOffice Draw
- StarOffice Impress
- StarOffice Writer
- VICAR (Video Image Communication and Retrieval) Planetary File Format
- WordStar for MS-DOS Document
- WordStar for Windows Document
- Wordstar 2000

formats: JSON, XML, PDF; Data Models: Datacite, Crossref, OpenAIRE, MEDLINE/PubMed

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

240 GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be combined with other data, hence a new dataset will emerge. The new dataset (to be described in the future iterations of the DMP) will use only a subset of the reused datasets, particularly information that is relevant to reproducibility and the TIER2 project objectives. The dataset will be analysed according to a set of indicators aiming to produce results that support informed decision and policy making, e.g. setting up the future actions on reproducibility.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Metadata are harvested from trusted sources and all links are kept with the original resource. New links created upon curation of the data in the Graph are also kept for every iteration of the algorithm during monthly updates. History of those changes and enhancements are made available to resource providers using the OpenAIRE PROVIDE service (<https://provide.openaire.eu/home>).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Economy

OpenAIRE data contain rich information about science and its evolution, especially on the Open Science realm. There are immediate and meso-/ long - term potentials from exploiting OpenAIRE Graph reused data from the perspective of reproducibility. They both are able to positively affect the research sector at different pace and levels:

- Researchers and research communities can use the data from the dump, in the same way that TIER2 is getting them, and they can build on top of them and analyse them based on their own scientific interests and objectives.

- Decision and policy makers can embed those data in their scientific ecosystems to influence and enhance intelligence policies for science.

- The economy will eventually flourish by keeping track of the evolution of reproducibility through periodic exploitation and enhancement of those data and their reproducibility algorithms, and by continuously healing identified gaps that mitigate reproducibility risks.

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers
- National identifiers

DOI

ORCID

OpenOrgs

Cordis

The full list of the PID types that the OpenAIRE Graph collects can be found here: https://api.openaire.eu/vocabularies/dnet:pid_types.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

OpenAIRE metadata format:

a. <https://zenodo.org/record/4723403>

Zenodo

b. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3974225>

Zenodo

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

MeSH (Medical Subject Headings)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

OpenAIRE vocabularies: <https://api.openaire.eu/vocabularies/>

COAR vocabularies, Datacite vocabularies, other vocabularies as indicated in the OpenAIRE guidelines

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Metadata repository
- Linked Open Data

Metadata about the OpenAIRE Research Graph is searchable via Zenodo and OpenAIRE itself (via explore.openaire.eu).

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Metadata harvestable via Zenodo.

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Repository hosted by Zenodo.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes, Zenodo resolves DOIs in the DOI resolver. Additionally, to create related identifiers with other outputs, Zenodo maintains the following list of resolvers:

https://github.com/inveniosoftware/idutils/blob/d29102410bd26be48dcac40d688659e2d19a7572/idutils/__init__.py#L962-L987.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

OpenAIRE Graph Dump

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

<http://api.openaire.eu/vocabularies>

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

The OpenAIRE Guidelines are used with the intention to provide a public space to share OpenAIRE's work on interoperability and to engage with the community. The [OpenAIRE Guidelines](#) help repository managers expose publications, datasets and CRIS metadata via the OAI-PMH protocol in order to integrate with OpenAIRE infrastructure and the Graph.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning

- Analyses
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

On the technical level, the procedures followed can be found at:

<https://graph.openaire.eu/about#architecture>.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Elli Papadopoulou (orcid:0000-0002-0893-8509)

Data Manager

5.1 Data Security

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: FAIRsharing dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

[FAIRsharing](#) is a curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies, across all disciplines. FAIRsharing guides consumers to discover, select and use these resources with confidence, and producers to make their resource more discoverable, more widely adopted and cited. FAIRsharing enables the FAIR Principles by promoting the value and use of data and metadata standards, and their use by databases. FAIRsharing is available via both human- and machine-accessible options. Access to the FAIRsharing metadata for computational purposes is described [here](#) and is covered by a CC-BY-SA 4.0 licence (see also [here](#)).

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

Creating and using curated metadata from the FAIRsharing standards, databases and policy registries to facilitate T3.2 in creating FAIRsharing collections and other records to be surfaced in the knowledge hub of T2.3. Using and curating metadata from the FAIRsharing policy registry to facilitate T4.2 and T4.4 in creating reproducibility checklists, policy and practice.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Across the research disciplines there are thousands of standards and several thousands of databases, designed to assist the virtuous data cycle, from collection to annotation, through preservation and publication to subsequent

sharing and reuse. As consumers of these standards and databases, it is often difficult to know which resources are the most relevant for your specific domain and needs. As producers, you want to be sure your standard or database is findable by prospective users, and recommended in data policies by funders, journals and other organisations.

With our growing and interlinked content, functionalities and endorsements, FAIRsharing is the most comprehensive informative and educational resource of standards, databases and policies. FAIRsharing is a web-based, searchable portal of three interlinked registries, containing both in-house and crowd-sourced manually curated descriptions of standards, databases and data policies, combined with an integrated view across all three types of resource.

This metadata is made publicly available via a REST API and in JSON format.

1.1.5 What is its format?

JSON

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

We will use the FAIRsharing metadata to create FAIRsharing collections of resources specific to the needs of TIER2, and we will curate parts of the registry

related to TIER2 work packages in order to contribute to organisational and resource mapping, integrate with other resources, and contribute to Reproducibility Checklist, policy and practices.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Each record is manually curated based on publicly-available information about the standard, database or policy it describes. This manual curation is done by in-house curators and community volunteers. These volunteers are further divided into maintainers (who are responsible for the resource being described) and community champions (who may edit records across their research domain of interest).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Other

FAIRsharing is a community-driven resource with users and collaborators across all disciplines. We work together with our stakeholders to enable the FAIR Principles by promoting the value and the use of standards, databases and policies. These stakeholders within TIER2 include:

- Developers & curators of resources and tools: Integration of their resources with ARGOS, the Reproducibility checklist, and/or the FAIRsharing collections that will be produced.

- Journal publishers, funders and other policymakers: TIER2, especially WP4, will be working closely with policymakers on a proposed “Reproducibility Checklist, policy and practices” intervention. For these policymakers, FAIRsharing can be used to understand the landscape of resources relevant to their implementors,

and also as a method of transmitting their requirements to them. For funders, this includes improvements to policies and creation/curation of the relevant FAIRsharing Collections. For publishers, this primarily involves the creation of the reproducibility checklist.

- Researchers, research data facilitators, librarians, trainers: For them, the utility of FAIRsharing will be in: FAIRsharing's contribution to the Reproducibility checklist, creation/curation of FAIRsharing Collections of standards and databases, and connectivity of FAIRsharing to ARGOS via T2.3.

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers

DOI

ORCID

ROR

DOIs are minted through DataCite ([more information](#)). As a trusted organisation with ORCID, these identifiers are used to aid [authentication](#), and as attribution for [maintainers](#) and [community champions](#). ROR ids are regularly mapped to FAIRsharing organisations and new organisations can be added via the ROR API directly into a FAIRsharing record ([more information](#)).

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

All calls to the FAIRsharing API return JSON that aligns with the [FAIRsharing metadata schema](#).

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

[FAIRsharing metadata schema](#)

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://github.com/FAIRsharing/subject-ontology> (see also <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b1xD9f>);
<https://github.com/FAIRsharing/domain-ontology> (see also <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.FSIfv8>); NCBI Taxonomy (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.fj07xj>)

The subject and domain ontologies draw upon over 50 community-developed ontologies across a variety of domains to help tag our records in a hierarchical way. The NCBI Taxonomy is used to provide taxonomic scope for our records, where appropriate.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

Metadata about FAIRsharing is available from FAIRsharing itself.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

REST API and OAI-PMH provided.

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification

- Follows repository standards
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Follows curation processes
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.3 Add certification(s)

ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resource

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [Reproducibility Diaries](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Diary entries written quarterly by five TIER2 consortium members concerning their thoughts, ideas and perspectives in relation to reproducibility issues, both in TIER2 and beyond.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The Reproducibility Diaries will be written as part of the project and aim to reflect on the development of thoughts and attitudes of project members during the project.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

The dataset offers a collection of personal thoughts and experiences from project partners' activities. It captures how project partners navigate their everyday life in different research endeavours, how aware they are of the elements that mitigate reproducibility risks, how they engage in practicing reproducibility and they operationalise this knowledge in discussion with others.

1.1.5 What is its format?

AbiWord Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

Data are collected to obtain information about project members' attitudes and practices in relation to reproducibility. They will subsequently be used to write a project self-assessment report that feeds into recommendations for how to organise international, multidisciplinary projects to foster reproducibility.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Digital, written diary entries in Word/pdf format, by project members of the TIER2 consortium.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

The reflections derived from the data may support researchers, research policymakers and their communities to optimally organise and coordinate international, multidisciplinary research projects in terms of reproducibility issues. The data will shed light on the practices that researchers could employ to foster reproducibility and the kind of concerns or obstacles they face when trying to implement these practices. This includes potential disciplinary or organisational barriers towards reproducibility and will henceforth inform future policymakers, researchers and their communities to smoothen the path towards increased reproducibility standards.

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://lumivero.com/products/nvivo/#:~:text=What%20is%20NVivo%3F,from%20their%20qualitative%20data%20faster.>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers

- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Cordis

A description of the dataset will be uploaded to Zenodo to obtain a DOI. Additionally, ORCIDs will be associated to authors and contributors both on Zenodo and on this DMP on ARGOS for information relevant to roles allocation concerning the reproducibility diaries dataset. The DMP includes also the grant id of the project and the link with the DMPid.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

An abstract, key words, and relevant project and provenance information will be provided.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

Metadata will be available through Zenodo.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Some exemplary keywords are: Diary entry, Reproducibility, multidisciplinary research, organisational challenges.

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Follows repository standards

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Given the sensitive and personal nature of the data, not all data will be shared. However, the processed data that can be securely shared will be openly available.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

All descriptive metadata will be openly accessible.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

Key words, abstract and project information will be drafted in line with other project outputs and use the vocabulary commonly used in the main project deliverables. The vocabulary used will specifically be based on the concepts and terminology described in Milestone 3.1 of the project.

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

The data consist of diary entries written by five project members on a quarterly basis throughout the project duration. Based on a flexible and open format, members write about their ideas, concerns, practices and discussions related to reproducibility issues, both related to the TIER2 project as well as beyond. Entries are written individually though they will also reflect on group discussions and interactions within and beyond the consortium. For more details on methodology, please consult project deliverable 1.3.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

An overview of data provenance will be provided, including dates and format of the diary entries. In addition, the final deliverable reporting on the data, will include detailed descriptions of the way in which the data were processed and analysed.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Set up of scientific and technical committee

The processed data will result in a self-reflection report by the end of the project. This report will be subject to internal project peer review by at least one consortium or advisory board member and the project coordinators.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Indirect cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Serge P. J. M. Horbach (orcid:0000-0003-0406-6261)

Data Manager

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

The actual data (i.e. the diary entries) will be stored on secured servers protected by passwords.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Data storage

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

For privacy reasons and because the data might contain sensitive and personal information about the project members, all data will be securely stored and is not openly accessible. A summary and analysis of the data will be included in the self-reflection report (D1.3).

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms

Due to the sensitive and personal nature of the data, no raw data will be openly accessible. Instead, the processed and analysed data will be shared through deliverable 1.3 and the metadata will be made openly available. In the latter, anonymisation of study participants will be carried out and consent will be asked from study participants to publish quotes from their diary entries.

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Integrative Review Materials

Template: Horizon Europe

A list/spreadsheet of DOIs of reviewed literature; a spreadsheet of extracted data from and process decisions about reviewed literature

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

We are generating new data in a list of DOIs of reviewed literature for an integrative review.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

The data are a list of DOIs gathered and reviewed for an integrative review of how reproducibility/replicability are conceived in relation to qualitative research, as well as which open science practices are discussed in relation to supporting reproducibility of qualitative research.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Basic Excel spreadsheet

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

The dataset will be compiled to conduct an integrative review of the literature surrounding reproducibility of qualitative methods.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

This dataset will be of interest to researchers studying the reproducibility of qualitative research and educators interested in teaching and supporting reproducibility of qualitative research.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

The resulting dataset will have been derived from conducting an integrative review using the Syrf platform: <https://syrf.org.uk/>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

The dataset will be archived on Zenodo.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

reproducibility, Open Science

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Reviewed DOIs for integrative review of reproducibility of qualitative research

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

It will remain hosted on Zenodo.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinitely.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

This dataset was generated using the method for an integrative literature review, as described here: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-030-37504-1>

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

This dataset will be archived on Zenodo.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Nicki Lisa Cole (orcid:0000-0002-6034-533X)

Data Manager

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Recommendations Delphi Process

Template: Horizon Europe

Interviews/transcripts from workshops; survey data from Delphi; Spreadsheets reporting (1) survey results; (2) first phase recommendations; (3) second phase recommendations; and (4) third phase recommendations.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

We are conducting a Delphi study to identify policy recommendations based on project results.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

This dataset includes qualitative data that consist of recorded videos, transcripts, and step-wise data charting that document discussions, debates and brainstorming of science policy recommendations to support reproducibility of research gathered during a multi-phased co-creative Delphi process, in response to the cumulative findings of the Tier2 project.

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Excel 95 Workbook (xls)

- Microsoft Word for Windows Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions

These data were collected to generate feedback and validation of Tier2 project findings, and to co-create unique recommendations for science policy-makers.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

The data contained herein may be instructive and/or useful to researchers, research communities, policy-makers and institutional leaders at higher education institutions interested in the reproducibility of research and how best to foster it.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers

- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

This dataset will be archived on Zenodo.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

reproducibility, Open Science, qualitative data

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Results of Delphi study to create recommendations for boosting reproducibility

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Guidance on qualitative data sharing:

<https://qdr.syr.edu/guidance/managing/preparing-data>

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

This dataset will be created using a co-creative modified Delphi process, as described here by the researchers:

<https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rsos.221460>

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

This dataset will be archived on Zenodo.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Nicki Lisa Cole (orcid:0000-0002-6034-533X)

Data Manager

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Futures Studies - Workshop results

Template: Horizon Europe

Workshop transcripts; completed miro boards; analysed/processed data

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

audio recordings of the workshops

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers

- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

<https://osf.io/c7ka6>

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Open Science Framework

osf.io

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal
- Supports back up
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Follows curation processes
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Participation information document

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

10 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

inductive content analysis

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Sharing data

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Codebooks

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

i dont know

Euro

Security

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Joeri Tjink (orcid:0000-0002-1826-2274)

Data Manager

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access

- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

upload on OSF

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

unknown

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Unknown

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [GESIS data](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

GESIS data that are relevant for the reproducibility studies of TIER2 will be reused.
Examples are:

- TweetsKB: a public RDF corpus of anonymized data for a large collection of annotated tweets. The dataset currently contains data for nearly 3.0 billion tweets, spanning more than 9 years (February 2013 - August 2022)

- ClaimsJG: a structured database which serves as a registry of claims. It provides an entry point for researchers to discover claims and involved entities, also providing links to fact-checking sites and their results

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To make informed decisions
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- The public

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Unknown

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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